

TECHNISCHE
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Loan Prediction using ML

LPML

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	
Version:	1.0
Status:	
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	

Loan Prediction using ML has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Loan Prediction using ML project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

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1.0	[dd.mm.yyyy]		

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

CONTRIBUTORS

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Content

1. Executive Summary	5
1.1. Introduction	5
1.2. Data Summary	5
1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse	5
1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users:	6
2. FAIR data	6
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	6
2.2. Making data accessible	8
2.3. Making data interoperable	9
2.4. Increase data re-use	10
3. Other research outputs	11
4. Allocation of resources	11
5. Data security	12
5.1. Storage and backup facilities	12
5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data	12
5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data	13
6. Ethical and legal issues	13
6.1. Personal data	13
6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership	Error! Bookmark not defined.
6.3. Ethical issues	13
7. Other issues	14

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

[name of data manager] will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Loan	Images	png	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Loan":

Outputs

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	loan-10k.lrn	TU Wien		no

Description for "loan-10k.lrn":

This dataset contains structured information about 10,000 loan applications. Each row represents one application, and columns include demographic attributes (such as gender, marital status, and education level) and financial attributes (such as applicant

income, loan amount, and credit history). The target variable indicates whether the loan application was approved or rejected. The dataset was used for training machine learning models to predict loan default risk. The file is provided in CSV format with labeled columns and no missing values.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data is generated through training and evaluation of machine learning models on structured loan application datasets. The input datasets, provided in CSV format, contain demographic and financial attributes of loan applicants. These datasets were uploaded to DBRepo and documented with detailed metadata. No external datasets were reused aside from the original training and test sets. The following methods and software were used: Data Preprocessing: Data cleaning, scaling, and label encoding were performed using Python libraries such as pandas and scikit-learn. Model Training and Evaluation: Logistic Regression, Random Forest, and XGBoost models were trained using scikit-learn (version 1.3.0) and XGBoost (version 1.6.2). Evaluation Metrics: Accuracy, F1-score (macro average), precision, recall, and confusion matrices were calculated using scikit-learn. Visualization: Training times and confusion matrices were visualized using matplotlib (version 3.7.1). Data Storage and Metadata Management: Input data was deposited into DBRepo, while trained models and output artifacts (e.g., performance metrics, plots) were stored in TUWRD with extensive metadata descriptions following FAIR4ML, Croissant, and CodeMeta standards. All analyses were conducted using Python 3.10 in a Jupyter Notebook environment. The full analysis workflow, including code, data loading, model training, and evaluation, is publicly available on GitHub/GitLab, ensuring reproducibility.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The data is organized in a structured, tabular format using CSV files. Each row represents a single loan application, and each column corresponds to a specific attribute, such as demographic or financial information. The input datasets (training and test data) are stored in DBRepo, and each dataset is assigned a persistent identifier (PID) for proper citation and tracking. Versioning is handled by maintaining separate records for different stages of the data lifecycle. If updates to the dataset become necessary (e.g., corrections or additional attributes), a new version will be uploaded to DBRepo with an incremented version number in the metadata and filename (e.g., loan-10k.v2.Irn.csv). The original dataset will remain available for reproducibility purposes. Similarly, output artifacts such as trained models and evaluation results are stored in TUWRD with clear versioning practices. Each model and output file is individually uploaded and described with metadata that includes the creation date, software versions, and data provenance information, ensuring traceability and reproducibility.

The following research outputs were produced during the experiment and made publicly available through the TUWRD repository, each assigned a Persistent Identifier (PID) to ensure traceability, discoverability, and reusability: Trained Logistic Regression model (.pkl file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/7stkt-n6r66> Trained Random Forest model (.pkl file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/310hb-b1b27> Trained XGBoost model (.pkl file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/6caqy-rta71> Training time comparison plot (.png file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/xnkf1-7e276> Confusion matrix for the best model (XGBoost) (.png file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/zx8g1-hn084> Model performance metrics table (.csv file): <https://doi.org/10.70124/1fkmb-p3z93> File Formats: The research data and results are available in standard, widely supported formats: CSV for datasets and performance tables, PKL (Pickle) for trained machine learning models, PNG for graphical figures. Licenses: Trained models (PKL files): licensed under CC0 1.0 to allow unrestricted reuse. Data tables and figures (CSV and PNG files): licensed under CC-BY 4.0. Keywords: To facilitate discovery, the following keywords are assigned to all outputs: "Loan Default", "Machine Learning", "Risk Prediction", "XGBoost", "Random Forest", "Logistic Regression", "Financial Risk Prediction". Metadata Standards: All metadata records are submitted alongside the data and models into the appropriate repositories (DBRepo and TUWRD). Metadata follow widely recognized standards: FAIR4ML for describing model provenance and training processes, Croissant for describing dataset structure and attributes, CodeMeta for providing machine-readable software and code metadata. These practices ensure that all data, models, and outputs are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable according to FAIR principles. The full source code, Jupyter notebook, and documentation related to model training and evaluation are publicly available at the GitHub repository: https://github.com/haso-h/loan_prediction_ml. The repository

includes a README file and is licensed under the MIT License to facilitate reuse and reproducibility. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow interdisciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus

contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-02-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it.

<https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The datasets are provided in standard CSV format and can be accessed and processed using any common data analysis software, such as Microsoft Excel, LibreOffice Calc, or programming languages like Python or R. To fully reuse the trained machine learning models (.pkl files), users will require a Python environment (version 3.10 or compatible) and the following libraries: scikit-learn (version 1.3.0) — for Logistic Regression and Random Forest models, xgboost (version 1.6.2) — for the XGBoost model, joblib — for loading serialized models. Additionally, to replicate the full experiment, users may utilize the publicly available Jupyter Notebook, which documents all steps including data loading, model training, evaluation, and visualization. The required libraries are listed in the accompanying README file and environment specifications are included to facilitate reproducibility.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow re-using, refining, or extending them?

- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Comprehensive documentation will be provided to validate the data analysis process and facilitate data reuse. The following documentation elements will be made publicly available: Jupyter Notebook: The entire model training and evaluation process is documented in a Jupyter Notebook, including code, data loading procedures, model training, evaluation metrics calculation, and plots generation. Comments within the notebook explain each step clearly. README Files: README files accompany both the input datasets and the output artifacts. They explain the dataset structure, attribute descriptions, model evaluation results, and instructions on how to reproduce the experiments. Metadata: Extensive metadata following FAIR4ML, Croissant, and CodeMeta standards is provided for all datasets and trained models, describing data provenance, software environments, input structures, and training processes. Parameter Settings: Hyperparameters used for training each machine learning model (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost) are documented both in the notebook and in the associated

metadata of trained models. Software and Versioning Information: All software libraries and their versions (e.g., Python 3.10, scikit-learn 1.3.0, XGBoost 1.6.2) are listed to ensure that the environment can be recreated precisely. Licenses and Access Conditions: Clear licensing information is provided for datasets, code, and trained models to guide users on permissible reuse scenarios. Together, these elements ensure that others can not only access and understand the data and models but also reproduce the entire analysis pipeline independently.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Coverage of costs:

...

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders] being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-

checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Coordinator (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU Wien's Campus IT. The data will be stored on TU Wien servers.

R1 (loan-10k.lrn) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

P1 (Loan) will be stored on Server Housing: With this service provided by TU.it, the server is housed in a dedicated TU.it server room with limited access and operated by our institute.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	writing

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R1	writing	writing	writing

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

In this project, we will process personal data (see section 1). R1 (loan-10k.lrn) will contain personal data. We will ensure compliance with data protection laws, by anonymisation of personal data for preservation and/or sharing.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: Hasudin Hodzic

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise. The research plan of the project was reviewed by an ethics committee / the TU Wien Research Ethics Committee / a similar body.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?